

تواتر التعددات الشكلية rs2106809 – rs1978124 في جين ACE2 و rs1799752 في جين ACE لدى
جمهرة من سوريين أصحاء ومرضى ارتفاع توتر شرياني وفرط خثار الدم
Frequencies of ACE2 rs2106809-rs1978124 and ACE rs1799752
Polymorphisms in A Cohort of Healthy and Syrian Patients with hypertension
and hypercoagulability

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الملخص Abstract:

قادت التّويعات بين الأفراد وبين الأعراق المحدّدة لخطورة كوفيد-19 إلى إجراء دراسات جينية واسعة النطاق لفهم التأثيرات المعقّدة بين النمطين الجيني والظاهري. اقترح سابقاً أن التعددات الشكلية في كلِّ من جيني الإنزيم المحول لأنجيوتنسين (ACE) والإنزيم المحول لأنجيوتنسين 2 (ACE2) ترتبط مع حالات ارتفاع التوتر الشرياني وفرط تخثر الدم التي قد تؤهب لشدة داء كوفيد-19. في دراسة الحالات والشواهد هذه، قمنا بتحري تواترات اثنين من التعددات الشكلية مفردة النوكليوتيد (SNPS)؛ rs2106809 و rs1978124 في جين ACE2، والتعدد الشكلي غرز/حذف (I/D) rs1799752 في جين ACE، وذلك في مجموعة من شواهد أصحاء سوريين (n= 48) ومرضى يعانون ارتفاع التوتّر الشرياني و/أو الخثار (n=35). استخلص الحمض النووي من عينات الدم وضخمت منتجات تفاعل البلمرة المتسلسل (PCR) النوعية الخاصة بالتعدّدات الشكلية المدروسة باستخدام زوجين من المشارع، ورُحلت كهربائياً على هلامة الأغاروز، وتلا ذلك سلسلة عيارية لاستعراف التعددين rs2106809 و rs1978124. تم حساب تواترات الألائل الكبرى والصغرى وكذلك الأنماط الجينية وتسجيلها. بلغت تواترات الأنماط الجينية الثلاثة في جمهرة دراستنا: 31.6% للأليل G rs2106809، و 57.9% للأليل C rs1978124، و 84.2% للنمطين الجينيين rs1799752 (DD + ID)، وكانت مغايرة بالمقارنة مع معدلات الانتشار المنشورة لدى الأوروبيين والأفارقة والآسيويين. حققت تواترات الأنماط الجينية في ذراع الشواهد الأصحاء توازن هاردي واينبرغ (HWE)، غير أنّها انحرفت عنها في جمهرة المرضى، مما يقترح وجود ارتباط بين تعدد الأشكال والحالات المرضية المدروسة. كان تواتر الأليل الأصغري/الثانوي rs2106809 أعلى (45.5%) لدى المرضى الذكور مقارنة بالذكور الأصحاء (17.2%)، مما قد يشير إلى وجود علاقة محتملة بين الأليل G وارتفاع ضغط الدم/الخثار. علاوة على ذلك، تظهر النتائج التي توصلنا إليها وجود فارق كبير في تواترات الأليل G بين الإناث والذكور. كان تواتر الأليل D rs1799752 والبالغ (75%) أعلى بثلاثة أضعاف من تواتر الأليل A (25%) لدى مرضى ارتفاع ضغط الدم والخثار الذكور، في حين كانت تواترات كلا الأليلين متساوية في المريضات الإناث. في الختام، تشير بياناتنا إلى وجود ارتباط محتمل بين ثلاثة تعددات شكلية للجينات

ACE2/ACE وحالتين مرضيتين يُعرف عنهما التَّسبب في تفاقم معدلات المراضة والوفيات الناجمة عن كوفيد-19. يمكن أن تساهم هذه النتائج في فهم أفضل لتنوعات الأنماط الجينية-الظاهرية بين الأفراد لدى السوريين.

Inter-individual and inter-ethnicity variations related to the severity of COVID-19 have led to extensive genetic studies to understand the complicated genotype-phenotype interactions. Polymorphisms in both angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) and ACE2 genes were previously proposed to be associated with hypertension and hypercoagulability states that could lead to COVID-19 severity. In this case-control study, we report the frequencies of two single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs); the rs2106809 and rs1978124 in the ACE2 gene, and the rs1799752 insertion/deletion (I/D) polymorphism in the ACE gene, in a cohort of Syrian healthy controls (n=48) and patients with hypertension and/or hypercoagulability (n=35). DNA was extracted from blood samples and polymorphism specific polymerase chain reaction (PCR) products were amplified using two sets of primers. Gel electrophoresis for all three polymorphisms- containing PCR amplicons was run followed by standard sequencing for the rs2106809 and rs1978124. Major and minor allele frequencies, as well as genotypes, were counted and recorded. The frequencies of all three polymorphisms; rs2106809 G allele (31.6%), rs1978124 C allele (57.9%), and rs1799752 DD+ID genotypes (84.2%) in our study population were divergent compared with prevalence reported in Europeans, Africans and Asians. The genotype frequencies in the healthy controls followed Hardy-Weinberg Equilibrium (HWE), however deviated from HWE in the patients, suggesting a potential link between the studied polymorphisms and these disease states. The frequency of the rs2106809 minor allele was higher (45.5%) in male patients compared to healthy males (17.2%), suggesting a possible association between the G allele and hypertension/thrombosis. Moreover, our findings demonstrate a considerable difference in allele frequencies between females and males. The frequency (75%) of the rs1799752 D allele was three times that of the I allele (25%) in hypertensive and thrombotic male patients, whereas the frequencies of both alleles were equal in the female patients. In conclusion, our data suggest a possible association between three ACE2/ACE gene polymorphisms and two disease states known to aggravate COVID-19 morbidity and mortality. These findings could contribute to a better understanding of the inter-individual genotype-phenotype variations in Syrians.

الكلمات المفتاح :Key words

ارتفاع الضغط، الخثار، ACE2، ACE، SNP، rs2106809، rs1978124، rs1799752

Hypertension, Thrombosis, ACE2, ACE, SNP, rs2106809, rs1978124, rs1799752

Introduction

The recent emergence of the Coronavirus (COVID-19) has constituted a global health emergency and quickly turned into a pandemic that swept across all continents of the world and caused acute respiratory syndrome that led to millions of deaths worldwide [1]. However, the clinical spectrum of SARA-Cov2 infection is broad and ranges from mild or moderate to severe lung injury, and multi-organ failure resulting in death, especially in elderly patients or those with other comorbidities [2,3]. A plethora of laboratories and clinical centers around the world has sought to understand the pathogenic mechanism(s) of Corona virus infection, and particularly to explain the

apparently considerable inter-individual and inter-ethnicity variations in severity and death toll. The first impetus of the viral invasion of target human cells is the binding of corona virus, via its spike protein, to its cellular receptor the "angiotensin-converting enzyme 2" (ACE2). In fact, researchers the past two decades have extensively investigated ACE2, and its genetic polymorphisms, as a key regulator of the renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS), and demonstrated the involvement of ACE2 in the pathophysiology of high arterial blood pressure and hypercoagulability states [4-8].

ACE2 is considered a negative regulator of the RAAS, due to its enzymatic activity that

catalyzes the hydrolysis of angiotensin I to angiotensin (1-9) and the direct cleavage of the vasoconstrictor angiotensin II into the vasodilator angiotensin (1-7) [9,10]. The hydrolysis of angiotensin I and II by ACE2 evidently controls the harmful effects of angiotensin I (Ang I) and angiotensin II (Ang II) on the cardiovascular system by reducing oxidative stress, and stimulating both vasodilatory and anti-fibrotic mechanisms [11,12].

Noteworthy, several clinical studies have reported disturbances in blood pressure control in hypertensive patients who develop COVID-19, and the underlying possible causes included restrictions on access to medical care, psychological distress, and lifestyle changes resulting from the pandemic [13]. Furthermore, a critical question emerged regarding the justifications of using antihypertensive agents, such as ACE inhibitors (ACEi) and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), in COVID-19 patients. Both ACEi and ARBs usually increase the expression of ACE2, and therefore may increase the virus entry into its target cells [14]. Additionally, seriously ill patients with COVID-19 were reported to develop hypercoagulability and clotting conditions, which render them susceptible to potentially fatal risk [3]. In fact, it has been suggested that binding of the coronavirus spike protein to the ACE2 receptor on the surface of blood platelets stimulates their activation and aggregation. This in turn may directly enhance platelet activation and contribute to thrombogenesis and inflammatory responses in COVID-19 patients and their development of cytokine storm associated with microvascular injury and thromboembolic inflammatory syndrome [15].

Among other discrepancies that emerged among COVID-19 patients was the clearly higher death rate among males compared to females [16-18]. The death rates were reported to be higher in men (4.7% and 16.6%) compared with females (2.8% and 9.1%) in Chinese and Italians, respectively [19,20]. One possible explanation for the higher mortality rates in males is that the ACE2 gene is located on chromosome X, and since males have only one copy of chromosome X. Hence, males may lose the cellular compensatory protection mechanism after exposure to corona virus compared to females whose extra X chromosome

might escape the inactivation mechanism [21]. This may also explain the male-female discrepancy in the levels of the ACE2 expression, as ACE2 expression is speculated to be higher in females [22]. In fact, it has been reported that the female hormone estrogen may increase the expression of ACE2 [23].

Being the most common type of genetic variation, single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs) are defined as a single nucleotide changes whose prevalence exceeds 1% in a given population. The ACE-2 gene and protein demonstrate high levels of genetic polymorphism, including SNPs, inter-individual variation in transcription efficacy, post-transcriptional modifications and putative protein mutations that could interfere with the binding of the coronavirus to its receptor ACE2 [24]. SNPs in the ACE2 gene could affect entry of the SARS-CoV-2 virus and thus the severity of COVID-19 disease. Nonetheless, some of these ACE2 polymorphisms were previously linked to susceptibility to cardiovascular diseases [7,12,25,26], and a sound argument is made that links these polymorphisms in ACE2 with disturbances in blood pressure and the hypercoagulability states associated with Covid-19 disease, and may contribute to better understanding of the inter-individual and inter-ethnic variations in clinical severity of the disease [27,28].

Equally important are polymorphisms in other genes encoding critical proteins in the RAAS, including the angiotensin-converting enzyme *ACE*, encoding an enzyme that converts Ang I to the hypertensive Ang II. SNPs in the ACE2 gene were identified by several research teams as ones of the most significant polymorphisms that may be related to the severity of COVID-19 [28]. In fact, among the most relevant polymorphisms previously studied are the rs2106809 (A>G) and rs1978124 (T>C) SNPs, both in intron I of ACE2 gene located in NG-012575 locus on chromosome X, and the polymorphism rs1799752 (or rs4646994) (D>I) present in intron 16 of the ACE gene in NG-011648 locus on autosomal chromosome 17q23.3 [29]. In fact, a 50 base pair (bp) Alu sequence is usually inserted in 6 copies with a corresponding 300 bp difference between the I allele (490 bp) and the D allele (190 bp) (www.snpedia.com). In an attempt to contribute to our understanding of the

mechanisms that might lead to the clinical variations in COVID-19 patients, our current study aims to determine the frequency of the above three polymorphisms in a cohort of Syrian patients with hypertension and hypercoagulability in comparison with their frequencies in a control group of healthy individuals.

Materials and Methods

Subjects and Samples

This observational case-control study included 81 non-related participants, 48 healthy individuals (29 males (M) and 19 females (F), average age 55 ± 19 years (mean \pm SD), and 33 patients (22 males and 11 females, 50.2 ± 13.5 years), with no significant statistical difference regarding average age between the two groups ($p = 0.16$ by student t-test). The cases encompassed 21 patients with hypercoagulability (deep venous thrombosis (DVT) and pulmonary embolism (PE)) (14 M and 7 F) and 14 patients with hypertension (10 M and 4 F), with two male patients having both conditions (DVT and elevated blood pressure). Our study was approved by both the Bioethics Committee at the Faculty of Pharmacy - Damascus University, and the National Committee for Ethics of Scientific Research and Novel Technologies (CONEST), at the Higher Commission for Scientific Research. Informed consents were obtained from all subjects prior to their enrollment. All participants were Syrian nationals from Damascus and Reef Dimashq governorates. Three milliliters of peripheral blood were collected on Ethylene Diamine Tetraacetic Acid (EDTA) and stored at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

DNA isolation and amplification

With the exception of DNA sequencing, the molecular work and genotyping processes were performed at the Pharmaceutical Biotechnology and Immunology laboratories- National Commission for Biotechnology, Damascus. Genomic DNA was isolated from blood samples using Qiagen blood DNA extraction kit (Qiagen, USA) according to the manufacturer's protocol. DNA concentrations and purity were assessed using Nano drop (Maestrogen®, Taiwan). In order to verify the quality and conservation of

isolated DNA, horizontal 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis was run followed by ethidium bromide staining (Promega®, USA).

We performed polymerase chain reaction (PCR) amplification using two sets of specific primer pairs. For both rs2106809 and rs1978124, we used forward primer 5` TGGTCAACCACACATACCACA 3` and reverse primer 5` AATGCTCTGGGAAAGCCAGAT 3`, with an expected amplicon size of 287 base pair (bp). For the rs1799752 (ACE I/D), we used forward primer 5` CTGGAGAGCCACTCCCATCCTTTCT 3` and reverse primer 5` GGGACGTGGCCATCACATTCGTCAG 3`, with expected amplicon sizes of 190 bp for the D allele and 490 bp for the I allele. All primers were manufactured by (Eurofins, Belgium), and were designed using Primer 3 software tool and checked prior to ordering using the MFE primer bioinformatics tool (<https://mfepimer3.igenetech.com/spec>) to evade any non-specific binding to genomic DNA. PCR was performed according to standard methods using thermal cycler (SENSEQUEST®, Germany) and 2X Master Mix (Genedirex®, Taiwan). The PCR reaction mixture contained 20 ng of genomic DNA and $0.25\text{ }\mu\text{m}/\text{l}$ of each primer. PCR amplification was performed according the following protocol including: initial denaturation for 5 min at 95°C , 35 cycles of (30 sec at 94°C , 30 sec at 57°C , and 1 min at 72°C), and a final 10 min at 72°C for final extension. PCR amplicons were analyzed by agarose gel electrophoresis, using an electrophoresis apparatus from (Cleaver, UK) and a 100 bp DNA size marker from (Genedirex®, Taiwan). DNA Sequencing was performed at (Macrogen, South Korea) according to standard protocols.

Bioinformatics & statistical analyses

Sequencing results were analyzed using bioinformatics tool (Geneious® software, USA). Genotype frequencies of sample alleles were estimated by gene counting method. The agreement with Hardy-Weinberg equilibrium (HWE) of the observed genotypic distribution for the ACE2 and ACE genes was tested by chi-square tests. Statistical analyses were performed using Microsoft EXCEL and Fisher Exact Test to compare the ratios of the genotype and allele

frequencies, respectively, with a p-value <0.05 as significant.

Results

Genotyping

The PCR amplification of both *ACE2* and *ACE* gene sequences was successful as amplicons appeared with the expected sizes as shown after gel electrophoresis (Fig. 1a and b). All *ACE2* amplicons appeared as single bands with the approximate size of 300 bp. The amplicons of the *ACE* gene appeared as i) a single approximately 500 bp band, for the insertion (I) homozygote, ii) a single around 200 bp band for the deletion (D)

homozygote, or iii) two bands around 500 and 200 bp for the (I/D) heterozygote.

Sequencing results of the *ACE2* amplicons revealed the presence of two variations at positions 256 and 258 from the 5' amplicon end related to SNPs rs2106809 and rs1978124, respectively (Figs 1. c-e), representing the three expected genotypes for both rs2106809 and rs1978124 SNPs; Fig. 1c (GG and CC), Fig. 1d (AA and TT), Fig. 1e (AG and CT), respectively. For the *ACE* rs1799752 I/D variation, genotyping was read according to differential sizes of the PCR products of the I and D alleles (presence or absence of the 200 bp and 500 bp bands).

Fig. 1. Gel electrophoresis and sequencing chromatograms results of PCR amplicons using gene specific primer pairs. (a) Gel electrophoresis of PCR amplicons for *ACE2* rs2106809 and rs1978124 SNPs showing a single band close to 300bp, M stands for 100 bp DNA marker. (b) Gel electrophoresis of PCR amplicons for *ACE* rs1799752 I/D showing two samples with the I/D heterozygote genotypes, and one sample each for II and DD homozygote genotypes. (c-e) Sequencing chromatograms for three samples showing the genotypes (GG-CC in c), (AA-TT in d), and (AG-CT in e) for both rs2106809 and rs1978124, respectively.

Genotypes for all three SNPS were extrapolated and recorded either from sequencing chromatograms, for the rs2106809 and rs1978124, or from gel electrophoresis, for the rs1799752. We compared genotype and allele frequencies for all three polymorphisms on the basis of gender and the health/disease status, thus, categorizing study subjects in [2 X 2] groups; healthy females, female patients, healthy males, and male patients (Table 1). In females, no significant differences in any of the three polymorphisms were observed between healthy and compromised females (p values >> 0.05 for all comparisons). In males, all comparisons showed no significant differences in allele frequencies except when comparing the frequencies of the rs2106809 SNP between healthy men and male patients; as male patients had significantly higher minor allele frequency (MAF) G compared to healthy controls (p= 0.035). Nonetheless, although mostly not significant, p values for allele frequencies in both male groups were considerably smaller compared with p values for all comparisons between the two female groups (healthy females

vs. female patients), with the latter being close to 1.

Noteworthy, the genotype distribution was in agreement with HWE for the rs1799752 in the controls (I.e., healthy female and male subjects (n= 48) (p=0.43). Remarkably however, rs1799752 genotype distribution among female and male patients showed clear deviation from HWE (p= 0.0014). For both rs2106809 and rs1978124, HWE cannot be conceived, as both SNPs are located in the X chromosome leading to discrepancy between males and females. Finally, we compared major (MAF) and minor (MAF) allelic frequencies for the rs2106809 and rs1978124 SNPs, in addition to the sum of both D and I allelic frequencies for the rs1799752, between the healthy female group reported in our current study and the previously published frequencies in several ethnic groups (Table 2). Statistical analyses revealed no significant differences regarding age, gender, allele and genotype frequencies between hypertensive versus thromboembolic patients (p values for all comparisons >> 0.05).

Table (1): Genotype and allele frequencies of the rs2106809, rs1978124, and rs1799752 in the total study subjects.

Polymorphisms	Females n (%)			Males n (%)			
	Healthy (n= 19)	Patients (n= 11)	p value	Healthy (n= 29)	Patients (n= 22)	p value	
rs2106809	Genotype	AA	10 (52.6%)	6 (54.5%)	---	---	0.96
		AG	6 (31.6%)	3 (27.3%)	---	---	
		GG	3 (15.8%)	2 (18.2%)	---	---	
	Alleles	A	26 (68.4%)	15 (68.2%)	24 (82.8%)	12 (54.5%)	1.0
G		12 (31.6%)	7 (31.8%)	5 (17.2%)	10 (45.5%)	0.035*	
rs1978124	Genotype	TT	5 (26.3%)	2 (18.2%)	---	---	0.87
		TC	6 (31.6%)	4 (36.4%)	---	---	
		CC	8 (42.1%)	5 (45.5%)	---	---	
	Alleles	T	16 (42.1%)	8 (36.4%)	16 (55.2%)	8 (36.4%)	0.79
C		22 (57.9%)	14 (63.6%)	13 (44.8%)	14 (63.6%)	0.26	
rs1799752	Genotype	II	3 (15.8%)	4 (36.4%)	4 (14%)	2 (9.1%)	0.16
		ID	12 (63.2%)	3 (27.3%)	13 (44.7%)	7 (31.8%)	
		DD	4 (21%)	4 (36.4%)	12 (41.3%)	13 (59.1%)	
	Alleles	I	18 (47.4%)	11 (50%)	21 (36.2%)	11 (25%)	1.0
D		20 (52.6%)	11 (50%)	37 (63.8%)	33 (75%)	0.28	

* Statistically significant

Table (2): Comparison of the major and minor allele frequencies (for rs2106809-rs1978124) and genotype frequencies (for rs1799752) in our study subjects versus different ethnic groups.

Polymorphisms		Our Study ^a	EUR	AFR	ASN
rs2106809	MaAF A	0.684	0.807 ^b	0.871 ^b	0.379 ^b
	MAF G	0.316	0.193 ^b	0.129 ^b	0.621 ^b
rs1978124	MaAF T	0.421	0.625 ^b	0.261 ^b	0.2 ^b
	MAF C	0.579	0.375 ^b	0.739 ^b	0.8 ^b
rs1799752	DD + ID	0.842	0.792 ^c	0.864 ^c	0.55 ^c

MaAF: major allelic frequency, MAF: minor allelic frequency EUR: Europeans, AFR: Africans, ASN: Asians. ^a: Data of healthy females in our study. ^b: Data from www.snpedia.com. ^c: Data from Kenyon et al [30]

Discussion

The results of the PCR amplification reactions followed by electrophoresis proved that the amplification process was successful as all amplification products appeared with the expected lengths. Sequencing chromatograms allowed for the detection of the two ACEII SNPs (rs2106809 or rs1978124) and designations of homozygosity or heterozygosity. The rs1799752 polymorphism and genotypes were straightforwardly established via gel electrophoresis based on size discrepancy of the I versus D amplicons.

The allelic frequencies of the three polymorphisms in healthy females compared with female patients were almost identical, with a p value almost reaching 1. Discrepancies in allele frequencies, however, were evident between healthy males and male patients, although only statistically significant for the rs2106809 polymorphism. Nonetheless, the clearly lower p values when comparing allele frequencies between the two male groups relative to females may indicate the presence of reasonable differences between the sexes in terms of the distribution of genotypes, with the main limitation of our study being the small number of the subjects that might have disguised statistical differences. On the other hand, our results indicate that HWE was applicable to genotype frequencies of the rs1799752 polymorphism in the healthy control group, including both females and males subgroups, but not in female and male patients. This deviation from HWE in the patient groups may indicate

genetic association between this polymorphism and the disease state phenotypes denoted in our sample by hypertension and thrombosis, as previously suggested by Royo et al [31].

Our results revealed that the frequencies of the major and minor alleles for the rs2106809 and rs1978124 SNPs in Syrians are distinctive compared with those reported in other racial groups (Table 2), noting that the frequency of the alleles for genes located on the X chromosome is calculated mainly in healthy females. As for the rs2106809 polymorphism, the frequency of the A allele in our cohort of healthy females was 0.684, which is lower than the frequencies reported in Europeans and Africans, but higher than that in Asians. Moreover, the frequency of the T allele for the rs1978124 polymorphism in our study was lower than that reported in Europeans, whereas higher than its prevalence in both Africans and Asians, where the ratio between major and minor alleles flipped. As for the rs1799752 polymorphism, we were unable to precisely define the frequencies of the individual major and minor alleles in other populations worldwide. Rather, we compared the summation values of the DD and ID frequencies in our study, which were almost equivalent to the frequencies of the two genotypes in Europeans and Africans, while higher than those in Asians [30]. One possible explanation for these results stems from the genetic admixture of modern-day Syrians who descended from a combination of multiple ancestries belonging to different ethno-religious groups (Arabs, Kurds, Turkmen, Assyrians, Circassians, Armenians, and others). Such DNA admixing can be at least partially result from

spatial and temporal processes of gene flow due to trade, migrations and war.

rs2106809 A>G

The trend of higher rs2106809 minor allele (G) frequency in healthy females compared with healthy males could suggest a possibly greater expression of the ACE2 receptor on cell surface in females and consequently an expected lower arterial blood pressure, as previously discussed by Li et al, [19]. In fact, it was previously shown that blood pressure levels in females were lower than their male counterparts at all ages, until the age 70s, when BP equalizes between males and females [32]. However, reasons other than ACE2 polymorphisms could be considered to explain this sexual bias in blood pressure, such as possible mechanisms by which androgens may increase blood pressure, the difference in estrogen levels and escaping the inactivation of the X chromosome, which could lead to higher ACE2 levels in females than males [20]. Noteworthy, this difference in expression levels of ACE2 receptor could also contribute to the variation in susceptibility to severe Covid-19 disease, taking into account that a previous report demonstrated higher severity of the disease in males compared with females [22].

In contrast to the dominating dogma, the G minor allele frequency was unexpectedly higher in our male patients (45.5%) compared to healthy males (17.2%). In fact, data from several previous reports supported an association between the AA, but not the GG genotype, with essential hypertension (EH) [14]. Pan et al documented association between the AA genotype with EH and higher levels of the low-density lipoprotein (LDL) and triglycerides (TGs) [26]. Moreover, Luo et al demonstrated that the G allele increased the expression of ACE2 gene *in vitro* and suggested that the G allele displayed a protective effect in Asian populations [1]. In concordance with the latter study, Choudhary et al reported that circulating ACE2 levels were higher in the GG or GA genotyped COVID-19 patients [35]. On the contrary, Hamet et al reported a significant association of the G allele with high blood pressure in a biobank of British patients over 50 years old [34]. In addition, Molina et al have recently reported that the minor allele G was associated with increased hospitalization rate for

COVID-19 patients, and considered the G allele as a risk factor for disease severity [35], while Çelik et al reported that rs2106809 polymorphism was not associated with the clinical outcome in COVID-10 patients [36]. Finally, as the overall genetic composition in various ethnicities could be different, we cannot not rule out different effects of this and other individual SNPs on the phenotypes taking into account the interference of other genetic elements.

rs1978124 T>C

As for the ACE2 rs1978124 SNP, no statistical differences were found between the four healthy and patient groups. In fact, the MAFs in female and male patients were identical, considering the presence of 22 alleles in each group, despite the difference in the number of subjects due to different X chromosome frequencies between females and males.

The rs1978124 is an intronic SNP in the ACE2 gene and has been reported in an *in silico* model to interfere with messenger RNA secondary structure leading to possible effects on both the stability and splicing of mRNA, hence, reducing ACE2 levels [37]. While it is yet to uncover the role of this SNP in hypertension or hypercoagulation etiology, the T allele was found to increase the risk of arterial hypertension and cardiovascular disease in different ethnicities, suggesting a protective role for the minor allele C [24]. Interestingly, it seems that the effect of the TC heterozygote genotype on either hypertension or COVID-19 morbidity is controversial. Females with the TC genotype have significantly lower circulating ACE2 level [25]. Moreover, Sheikhan showed that TC genotype was related to COVID-19 mortality in Omicron BA.5 and alpha Corona variants [38]. In Iranian patients, the TT and CT genotypes were positively associated with susceptibility to COVID-19, while both genotypes had a protective effect that was limited to females [24]. Similarly, Molina et al showed a protective effect of the TC genotype over both TT and CC genotypes with regard to the severity of COVID-19 disease in Spanish patients [35]. In fact, the decrease in ACE2 receptors might play a role in decreasing the entry of the virus with a possible protective role in COVID-19. However, it is yet to determine the effect of this SNP in the

susceptibility to hypertension and hypercoagulability, although a decrease in ACE2 levels might suggest a protective role for this SNP in the context of susceptibility to hypertension.

rs1799752 D>I

Although our findings concluded no significant differences in allele frequencies between females and males, it is noteworthy that the allele frequencies were very similar in females, or literally identical, whereas the frequency of the D allele was two-to three-fold that of the I alleles in male healthy controls and patients, respectively. In fact, the D allele was reported to be associated with increased production of the vasopressor angiotensin II and a shorter half-life of the vasodilator bradykinin, leading to hypertension [39]. In addition, Zambrano et al reported that the DD genotype was associated with increased predisposition to hypertension compared with the ID and II genotypes [40]. Interestingly, Pachocka et al reported that individuals carrying the DD genotype had increased salt intake of more than 5 g/day compared to other genotypes, making them more prone to the risk of hypertension [41].

As for COVID-19 status, Saengsiwaritt et al reported in a recent meta-analysis that the DD-genotype carriers had a significantly increased risk of developing severe COVID-19 [42]. In concordance, Yamamoto et al reported that ACE1 II genotype negatively correlated with the number and severity of COVID-19 cases [43], while Gomez et al demonstrated a strong association between severe COVID-19 and both hypertension in males and their carrying the DD genotype [29].

Our data might be in agreement with the previous findings. In fact, we reported a 3 fold higher frequency of the D allele compared to the I allele in male patients, compared to identical frequencies of the two alleles in female patients. Additionally, we found a higher frequency of the DD genotype and lower frequency of the II genotypes in male compared to female patients (Table 1). Nevertheless, our data may be in disagreement with reported results by Faridzadeh et al who demonstrated a higher mortality rates in individuals with the I/D compared to the DD genotype in Iranians [24], and with those published by Celtic et al who

found no correlation between the DD genotype and COVID-19 severity in Turkish patients [38]. Finally, we found no previous data demonstrating any correlation between rs1799752 and hypercoagulability/thrombosis.

Conclusions

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study reporting the frequencies of three polymorphisms in two of the RAAS related genes that could be associated with multiple morbidities, including two in *ACE2* gene, rs2106809 and rs1978124, and one in *ACE* gene, rs1799752 I/D in Syrians. The frequencies of all three SNPs according to our findings were comparable to those previously documented in Europeans but considerably different from the prevalence in both Africans and Asians, especially those for the rs1978124. Despite the major limitation of our study being the small sample number, we have reported a significantly higher minor allele G frequency for the rs2106809 SNP in male patients compared with healthy males, suggesting a potential role for the G allele in the disposition to hypertension and/or hypercoagulability. Our data demonstrate a considerable allele discrepancy between females and males, although not statistically significant, suggesting gender differences in regards to the effects of these three SNPs on the phenotypes. Our study may pave the way for further investigation and clinical studies recruiting larger number of Syrian patients and controls in an attempt to link inter-patient genetic variations with predisposition to several diseases such as hypertension, thrombosis, cardiovascular disease and COVID-19.

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